

Perfluorinated polymer fibre Bragg grating sensors for distributed low dose clinical X-ray measurements

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ABSTRACT

Optical fibres have played an important role in the advancement of real-time dosimetry in clinical applications in recent years. Significant work has been done to increase precision and accuracy in detecting radiation doses during treatment, to avoid the negative effect that can ensue from irradiating healthy tissue around the tumour. The drive to develop distributed measurement in optical fibres has been limited to the slow scanning speed systems from optical time domain reflectometry (OTDR), however for radiotherapy dosimetry, with often short radiation pulse durations, fibre Bragg grating (FBG) interrogation is a better alternative because of the fast-scanning speed. The work presented here includes the preliminary results in the characterisation of CYTOP FBGs on exposure to X-ray radiation emitted from a clinical linear accelerator (linac) machine. A blue shifted linear response of the Bragg wavelength with sensitivity of 6.655 pm/Gy, 6.519 pm/Gy and 7.153 pm/Gy at the three main peaks (1522 nm, 1542 and 1561 nm), was recorded for a 9 Gy of radiation at a dose rate of 1.758 Gy /min with an amplitude fluctuation within the duration of radiation. The response demonstrates the potential for its use in low dose radiation dosimetry, providing for quasi-distributed sensing in radiotherapy.

Keywords: Optical fibres, Dosimetry, Fibre Bragg grating, X-ray, CYTOP, Radiation Monitoring, X-ray, fibre optics sensors, fibre optics dosimetry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Real time detection of radiation field during radiotherapy is a way to mitigate the effect of over-exposure of tissue and the irradiation of healthy surrounding tissues. Dosimeters based on optical fibres have been reported to be effective in the detection of small fields of irradiation [1]. In clinical applications, polymer optical fibres (POF) are preferred because of their robustness, ease of handling in comparison to glass and their near water equivalence. Extensive research has been undertaken on polymethacrylate (PMMA) fibre; the applicable sensors are typically based on different geometries of scintillating materials attached to the tip of the fibre. The optical fibre usually serves as a light signal transport medium; the scope of its deployment is limited because of the fabrication techniques as well as the integration of the materials into the fibre and the scintillators are prone to quenching after a certain dose [2].

The effect of radiation on the intrinsic properties of the material has also been used for radiation monitoring and it has been reported that the sensitivity from the measured radiation induced attenuation (RIA) in both the visible and infrared wavelengths is higher in Perfluorinated polymer optical fibre (PF-POF) in comparison to PMMA fibre [3,4]. The intrinsic attenuation of PMMA in the infrared region is very high thus limiting its use in distributed sensing with available distributed measuring system such as the Optical Time domain reflectometry (OTDR) and Optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR) operating at the telecommunication window (1550 nm) interest.

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PF-POF are made to be transparent in the infrared region by the replacement of the hydrogen bond in the C-H bond with fluorine to form C-F bonds [5], making them useful for distributed measurement and the proof of concept has been reported by Stajanca et al.[4] The drive to develop distributed measurement in optical fibres has been limited to the slow scanning speed systems from optical time domain reflectometry (OTDR), however for external beam radiotherapy dosimetry, with often short radiation pulse durations, fibre Bragg grating (FBG) interrogation is a better alternative because of the potential for a fast-scanning speed.

The inscription of periodic structure into the core of the fibres (Fibre Bragg grating) can potentially be used for quasi-distribution sensors [6,7] and previous work by Broadway *et al* [5], on the sensitivity of FBGs in CYTOP fibre to gamma radiation, shows a huge potential for monitoring large doses of radiation (> 41 kGy) in harsh environments. Integrating FBG in POF for real time clinical application requires an effective sensitivity of the FBG to low dose of radiation that typically falls into the range of 2Gy for daily treatment. To the author's knowledge, the response of CYTOP FBG to low doses of X-ray for clinical applications has not yet been reported.

The effect of low dose radiation on FBGs in perfluorinated polymer is reported in this paper as a preliminary work to quasi-distributed measurement of radiation with a polymer fibre.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The optical fibre used in this experiment is a custom-made gradient index Cyclic perfluorinated (CYTOP) polymer fibre from Chromis with a femtosecond inscription of grating by Cyprus University of Technology, Cyprus [8]. The fibre has a core diameter of 50 μm and a cladding diameter of 490 μm with 3 FBGs at a length of 2mm and central wavelength of 1522 nm, 1542 and 1561 nm. A 1 m length of the fibre was mechanically spliced to an SMF-28 pigtail using a UV gel curing method and connected to a second fibre to extend the light signal to the safe zone outside the irradiation room which is approximately 20 meters. The interrogation of the FBG was with a Bayspec wave capture FBG interrogator operating over a wavelength range from 1510nm to 1590 nm, at an integration time of 1 ms and a sampling rate of 20Hz. The FBG was placed on a water equivalent phantom material at a source to surface distance (SSD) of 100cm. The radiation delivered to the fibre is from an Elekta Versa HD linear accelerator located at the Department of Radiotherapy, Galway Clinic, Galway, Ireland. A total dose of 3000 monitoring unit (9 Gy; 1 MU = 0.3 cGy) at SSD energy of 6 MV at an average dose rate of 586 MU/ min was delivered to the fibre. An overview of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Experimental setup

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The POFBG was aligned to the centre of the beam and irradiated with a $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ flattened filtered beam produced by the linac at an energy of 6 MV. The maximum intensity algorithm, which considers the maximum intensity for each spectral and the corresponding wavelength, was used for the analysis of the effect of the radiation on the FBG spectra. The changes in the FBG spectra before and after 9 Gy of irradiation is shown in Figure. 2a.

Figure 2: (a) Spectral of the CYTOP FBG before and after irradiation with 9 Gy (b) Change in the fitted spectrum at an interval of 3 Gy (: insert zoomed spectral of central peak) (c) Bragg wavelength shift during irradiation (d) Intensity drop of the peak during radiation (subtracted from the initial intensity before radiation)

From the raw data obtained from the interrogator, no significant Bragg wavelength shift (BWS) was observed except periodic spikes across the peak wavelength this as a result of the resolution of the raw data from the Bayspec interrogator which falls within the range of 180 pm/px . The resolution of the spectra was improved by processing each spectrum with a spline interpolation and a Gaussian fit (Figure 2b). There was a slight improvement of the Bragg wavelength shift as the changes in the spectra during the period of radiation was seen and it was stepwise linear within the range of 70 pm. The stepwise BWS was removed by resampling the data by a factor of 667 to improve the resolution and to account for a minute wavelength shift in the spectra peak. The wavelength shift was consistent to 70pm and a linear response of the BWS with an increasing dose was obtained for the three subsequent peaks as shown in Figure 2c. By fitting a linear fit into the BWS, a sensitivity of 6.655 pm/Gy, 6.519 pm/Gy and 7.153 pm/Gy with squared correlation coefficient, R^2 value of 0.9948,

0.9956 and 0.9909 was obtained from the three peaks. The three Bragg peaks is blue shifted as the radiation increases this is consistent with the report by Broadway et. [9] although for a higher dose of Gamma radiation. The effect of the radiation on the peak optical intensity of the 3 FBG spectra follow similar patterns. There was an initial fluctuation in the intensity and a subsequent reduction in the intensity as the radiation dose increases (Figure 2d). This behaviour was observed in subsequent measurement and could be attributed to the erasure of the grating resulting from the radiation.

The measurement was taken within a clinical environment and the sensor was handled with care so that the physical parameter such as strain and humidity was eliminated during the irradiation process. Therefore, the blue shift in the FBG observed cannot be attributed to a physical parameter and the possible reason is the increase in temperature at the region of irradiation since the FBG array was irradiated by the X-ray. The same effect was reported by Broadway et. [9] of the negative thermo-optical coefficient displayed by the CYTOP material. Further investigation will be done to verify this phenomenon

FBGs in CYTOP fibre are robust for quasi-distributed sensing in clinical application as they show a consistent shift in the Bragg wavelength as the radiation dose from the linac increases.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, CYTOP PO-FBG were explored when subject to irradiation on an Elekta clinical linac machine. The CYTOP fibre was inscribed using femto-second laser with three main FBG peaks at a wavelength of 1522 nm, 1542 and 1561 nm . The result demonstrates that CYTOP PO-FBG are sensitive to low dose X-ray photons, with a linear blue shifted Bragg peak with sensitivity of 6.655 pm/Gy, 6.519 pm/Gy and 7.153 pm/Gy and a reduction in the intensity of the peak as a result of the radiation. It has demonstrated a potential for use in real-time in-vivo quasi-distributed dosimetry. Further investigation will be conducted with a high-resolution interrogator to quantify the response of the sensor for real time dosimetry.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Galway Clinic for the use of their facilities. The authors would like to acknowledge the support of the Royal Society and Science Foundation Ireland, through the Royal Society – SFI University Research Fellowship, UF150618, and the Royal Society – SFI Enhancement Award, RGF\EA\180166. This also work received funding from the Horizon 2020 programme of European Union (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions - Individual Fellowships) under REA grant agreement No. 844618 (project POSPORI), the Cyprus Research and Innovation Foundation (EXCELLENCE/0918/0324 “T-Sense”).

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